

Notes

Metal Complexes of 4-Dimethylaminomethylantipyrine with Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II)

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Metal complexes of antipyrine¹, 4-aminoantipyrine and pyrimidon² have been studied earlier. In all the above cases the ligand was found to act as a monodentate ligand bonding through its carbonyl oxygen which was further confirmed by spectral studies^{2,3}. Antipyrine can be converted to an effective chelating ligand by substituting dimethylaminomethyl group by Mannich reaction³ and the product obtained is dimethylaminomethylantipyrine (DMAMA). Literature survey showed no previous report of metal complexes of DMAMA. DMAMA (1) acts as a bidentate ligand and forms six-membered chelate (2) on complex formation.

(1)

(2)

Results and Discussion

Analytical data and other properties of the ligand and complexes are given in Table 1.

All the complexes are stable in solid state, and soluble in methanol, acetone and dimethylformamide. The stoichiometries of the complexes were found to be $[\text{Fe}(\text{DMAMA})_3]\text{Cl}_3$, $[\text{Co}(\text{DMAMA})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{DMAMA})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Zn}(\text{DMAMA})\text{Cl}_2]$. The

conductance data indicate that the Fe^{III} complex is a 1 : 3 electrolyte, Co^{II} complex is a 1 : 2 electrolyte, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are nonelectrolytes. The room temperature magnetic moment for the Fe^{III} complex (5.9 B.M.) shows the high-spin octahedral configuration, the Co^{II} complex (5.20 B.M.) the tetrahedral configuration and the value of the Cu^{II} complex (0.75 B.M.) may be due to strong metal-metal interaction.

Fe^{III} being a d^5 system the electronic spectrum for the complex does not show any peak, but the colour may be due to the charge transfer transition. The absorption peaks obtained at 21 186, 19 087 and 14 705 cm^{-1} for the Co^{II} complex can be assigned to $A_2 \rightarrow T_1 (P)$, $A_2 \rightarrow T_1 (F)$ and $A_2 \rightarrow T_2$ transitions, which confirm the tetrahedral configuration. A broad band for the Cu^{II} complex at 11 904 cm^{-1} corresponds to $T_{2g} \rightarrow E_g$ transition of d^9 tetrahedral system.

The ir bands for the free ligand appear at 1 650–1 670 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and 1 140–1 160 and 1 180 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}$). In all the complexes of DMAMA, the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}}$ are shifted to lower values by about 30 and 10–20 cm^{-1} respectively, which reveals the bidentate nature of DMAMA bonding through carbonyl oxygen and tertiary nitrogen. The appearance of non-ligand bands at 350 cm^{-1} for the Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{Cl}}$ which supports the results obtained from conductance data. The $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ bands for all the complexes lie in the range 325–380 and 300–305 cm^{-1} respectively.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Metal % Found/(Calcd.)	Cl	Ligand	Conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
$[\text{Fe}(\text{DMAMA})_3]\text{Cl}_3$	Dark brown	6.22 (6.06)	81.81 (82.26)	11.87 (11.66)	300 (MeOH)
$[\text{Co}(\text{DMAMA})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Peacock blue	9.50 (8.92)	79.03 (79.07)	11.45 (12.01)	200 (MeOH)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{DMAMA})\text{Cl}_2]$	Brown	16.73 (17.13)	64.56 (63.56)	18.71 (19.22)	70 (MeOH)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{DMAMA})\text{Cl}_2]$	Colourless	17.14 (16.98)	64.24 (64.94)	18.62 (18.01)	9.0 (DMF)

NOTES

The TG patterns show that all the complexes are thermally stable upto 300°. In all the cases the thermal decomposition takes place in two stages, finally yielding the corresponding metal oxide. Existence of some intermediate complexes/products have also been inferred from the percentage of weight-loss which is in agreement with the theoretical value and it requires further studies for giving conclusive evidences in support thereof.

The antibacterial activity was studied for DMAMA and its complexes by serial tube dilution technique⁴ and the percentage inhibition calculated using streptomycin as control. Both the free ligand and its Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were found to be active against *Escherichia coli* and *Streptococci* and the order of activity was [Co(DMAMA)₂]Cl₂ > DMAMA > [Zn(DMAMA)₂]Cl₂ > [Fe(DMAMA)₃]Cl₃.

Experimental

DMAMA was prepared³ by mixing formaldehyde with an aqueous solution of antipyrine and dimethylamine in 1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio in presence of one equivalent of concentrated HCl at 5°. The free base was obtained by treating the hydrochloride salt with excess aqueous KOH followed by extraction with CHCl₃. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the resulting colourless crystalline solid was dried, m.p. 169°.

Non-aqueous solution (ethanol or acetone) of the metal chloride was treated with alcoholic solution of the ligand in 1 : 3 mole ratio in the case of the Fe^{III} complex and 1 : 2 mole ratio in the case of the Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. The

Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complex were obtained after evaporation to dryness and the Zn^{II} complex as a precipitate. Complexes were purified by washing with ethanol and benzene and dried under reduced pressure.

Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M DMF and methanolic solutions using a Systronics conductivity Bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (acetone) on a JASCO UVIDEK-430 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The thermal data were obtained using a Shimadzu TG-DTA analyser and a Mettler-TG 3000 instrument. The chemical analysis of the complexes were done using standard procedures⁵. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method. Metals are estimated using both volumetric and gravimetric procedures. The amount of ligand was determined by elemental analysis of carbon.

References

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